

Non-specific solvent effects on proton transfer equilibrium between toluic acids and carbinol base of crystal violet

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Manuscript received 27 April 2009, accepted 20 August 2009

Abstract : Acid-base reactions in apolar aprotic media provide a sufficiently close measure of intrinsic acid/base strengths. A study on reaction equilibria between *o*- and *m*-methyl benzoic (toluic) acids with the carbinol base of crystal violet in five apolar aprotic solvents of similar Kirkwood polarity function $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ and significantly different Dimroth-Reichardt's $E_T(30)$ and Kamlet-Taft's polarity-polarisability π^* parameter indicates strongly the overall non-specific solvent effects are contributed by both electrostatic and dispersion interactions, the latter having a more dominant role therein.

Keywords : Apolar, aprotic, crystal violet, carbinol base.

Introduction

Acidity/basicity of a substance as conventionally measured in water and other polar solvents does not truly reflect the intrinsic acidity/basicity of its molecule owing to strong solvent effects due to specific solute-solvent interactions like hydrogen bond donor-acceptor or electron pair donor-acceptor interactions. However, a sufficiently close estimate for the intrinsic acidity of a substrate can be obtained by determining its acid strength in apolar aprotic solvents where specific solute-solvent interactions are minimized and the proton transfer is expected to be direct. In fact, the susceptibility of the strength of a set of *o*- and *m*-substituted benzoic acids to the structure of substituents when transferred from water to toluene, a typical apolar aprotic solvent, undergoes respectively 3-fold and 8-fold magnifications^{1,2} as compared to 3-fold and 9-fold magnifications respectively when transferred from water to the 'solvent free' gas phase³. The toluene-phase strength of an acid was measured conveniently in reference to the carbinol base of crystal violet dye (4,4',4''-tris dimethyl amino triphenyl carbinol) by monitoring the formation of the coloured ion-pair product spectrophotometrically.

The acid (HA)-dye carbinol base (Dye-OH) reaction in an apolar aprotic solvent producing the ion-pair (Dye⁺A⁻) would obviously be influenced by dipolar/electrostatic interactions between the solute and solvent mole-

cules. However, it needs probing whether non-electrostatic interactions like dispersion forces would contribute significantly or not to the gross non-specific solvent effects of the reaction.

In the present study the emphasis has been given to investigate the aforesaid aspects on proton transfer equilibria between *o*- and *m*-methyl benzoic acids and the carbinol base of crystal violet in five apolar aprotic solvents having similar dielectric constant (ϵ) and dipole moment (μ) but significantly different refractive index (n) and solvent polarity-polarisability parameter (Dimroth-Reichardt's, $E_T(30)$ and Kamlet-Taft's, π^*)⁴ (Table 1). The observations and findings of the research are presented as hereunder.

Experimental

The chemicals and solvents used were either of analytical reagent grade or highly purified by standard procedures⁵. The solution of the carbinol base crystal violet in an apolar aprotic solvent was prepared by basification of a $10^{-5} M$ aqueous solution of crystal violet with $\sim 2 M$ NaOH followed by extraction into the apolar aprotic solvent following a standard procedure⁶.

The reaction equilibria between *o*- and *m*-methyl benzoic acids, toluic acid (10^{-4} - $10^{-2} M$) and crystal violet carbinol base (10^{-6} - $10^{-5} M$) in dry benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane were moni-

tored at 28.0 ± 0.1 °C by absorbance measurements of the coloured ion-pair product at 610 nm in a Shimadzu 160A UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer. The molar absorptivity ($10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of crystal violet cation at 28.0 ± 0.1 °C were found to be 6.1, 5.9, 5.3, 3.4, 2.8 in benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane respectively.

Results and discussion

o-/*m*-Methyl benzoic acid (HA)-crystal violet carbinol base (Dye-OH) reaction :

can be symbolized as

(where D represents the colourless carbinol base and $\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-$ the coloured ion-pair) since the water molecule formed is hydrogen bonded to one of the species present in the equilibrium and they exist as one entity^{6,8-14}. The equilibrium data for *o*- and *m*-methyl benzoic acids in all the five solvents fit nicely with

$$K = \frac{(\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-)}{(\text{D})(\text{HA})^m} \quad (2)$$

The association constant ($\log K$) and the acid exponent (m) were determined from the least squares linear plots of $\log (\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-)/(\text{D})$ vs $\log (\text{HA})$. The indicator ratio $(\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-)/(\text{D})$ was measured as $(\text{Xe}/\text{B-Xe})$ where Xe and B are the absorbance of $\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-$ at equilibrium and on complete conversion of D, the dye carbinol. The values of $\log K$ and m along with solvent parameters are compiled in Table 1. The deviation in the values of the acid exponent (m) from unity is attributed to the overlapping participations of the reactive forms of the acid (HA) in

apolar aprotic solvents the monomeric acid, HA and the stronger homoconjugate acid-acid anion complex acids, $\text{H}^+(\text{A}^- \cdots \text{HA})$, $\text{H}^+\{\text{A}^- \cdots (\text{HA})_2\}$ etc.^{6,7}. The symbol $\text{DH}^+ \text{A}^-$ thus represents the ion-pair irrespective of the magnitude of m , the absorbance of the ion-pair insignificantly dependent on m . Similar observations were reported for proton transfer equilibria in benzene/toluene media for a variety of acids^{1,8-12} ranging from simple carboxylic acids and phenols to complex hydrogen spiroborates and also for different triarylmethane dye carbinols^{6,13}.

The association constant (K) is a concentration ratio and not a true thermodynamic constant (eq. (2)). Thus $\log K$ values can be employed to compare the effects of different solvents when the differences among the m values are not sufficiently large. The m values observed for *o*- or *m*-methyl benzoic acid in the five solvents are close enough (Table 1) to justify the use of $\log K$ to estimate relative solvent effects on the acid-carbinol base reaction.

On comparing $\log K$ for either *o*- or *m*-methyl benzoic acid with different solvent polarity parameters or functions such as ϵ , μ and the Kirkwood function $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ no regularity could be observed in the variation of $\log K$ with any of these parameters (Table 1). On the other hand a trend is noticeable in the variation of $\log K$ with solvent refractive index (n), and solvent polarity-polarisability parameter (Dimroth-Reichardt's, $E_T(30)$ and Kamlet-Taft's, π^*)⁴ (Table 1) indicating to a role by dispersion interactions. Interestingly, a distinct linear variation of $\log K$ with solvent polarity-polarisability parameter $E_T(30)$ and π^* could be observed with either of the acids. Thus, dispersion interactions blended with dipolar/electrostatic ones in a proportion similar to that in the empirical $E_T(30)$ and π^* parameter, would explain the

Table 1. Association constant ($\log K$) and acid exponent (m) for reaction equilibria between *o*- and *m*-methyl benzoic acids and crystal violet carbinol base in benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane along with their solvent parameters

Solvent	μ (10^{-3} cm)	ϵ	f (ϵ^a)	n	f (n^2) ^b	π^*	$E_T(30)^c$	$\log K$		m	
								<i>o</i> -Toluic acid	<i>m</i> -Toluic acid	<i>o</i> -Toluic acid	<i>m</i> -Toluic acid
Benzene	0.0	2.275	0.230	1.5011	0.228	0.59	34.3	2.03	1.99	1.10	1.01
Toluene	1.0	2.380	0.240	1.4969	0.226	0.54	33.9	1.96	1.84	1.19	0.93
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.0	2.270	0.229	1.4958	0.226	0.43	33.1	1.80	1.66	1.16	0.92
Carbon tetrachloride	0.0	2.238	0.226	1.4602	0.215	0.28	32.4	1.55	1.42	1.10	0.83
Cyclohexane	0.0	2.020	0.202	1.4262	0.204	0.00	31.2	1.21	1.10	1.04	0.78

$$^a f(\epsilon) = (\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$$

$$^b f(n^2) = (n^2 - 1)/(2n^2 + 1)$$

$$^c E_T(30) - \text{Ref. 4.}$$

non-specific solvent effects on the acid-dye carbinol base equilibrium. The polarisability parameter $(n^2 - 1)/(2n^2 + 1)$ being blended with the polarity parameter $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ in 5.5 : 4.5 ratio in the π^* parameters of apolar aprotic solvents as found by its two parameter regression analysis, the present study leads to the inference that acid-dye carbinol base reactions are promoted by an apolar aprotic solvent under two modes of solute-solvent interactions.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. S. K. Sen Gupta, former Professor and Head, Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (India) for valuable help and suggestions.

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